

Technology surveillance of the solar refrigeration by absorption/adsorption

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Technology surveillance of the solar refrigeration by absorption/adsorption (Conference Paper)

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Abstract [View references \(30\)](#)

In order to establish networks of cooperation looking for not to duplicate research and even to make use of existing research in a remote form, it is necessary to identify and classify (around the world) the researchers and laboratories, that are researching in the topic of solar refrigeration by absorption/adsorption. The methodology consists in: i) the technology's classification, ii) technological trajectory Identification, iii) a thematic bibliographic review, and iv) patent's analysis. In this way, with the previous determination of keywords, will be identified main authors and their respective institutions. With the same keywords, are determined the licensed patents (in certain span of time). In addition, the analysis of publications, patents, and commercial products give us an opportunity to establish comparisons between prototypes and tests (in several conditions). The larger results implicate the use of actor's network and the remote access to the data and tests, for a collaborative research, overcoming the lack of laboratory resource and accelerating the knowledge acquisition. © 2016 Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering and Technology, Inc.

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